

Towards a Better Understanding of Personas in the NFDI Interdisciplinary Context

4DS & 4Health pilot project

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Abstract

Within the NFDI consortia, understanding user needs within diverse research communities through the establishment of personas is crucial for designing effective research infrastructure [1-3]. However, the challenge of defining personas extends beyond individual domains—it requires a nuanced approach that accounts for the complexities of interdisciplinary collaboration [4]. Furthermore, in interdisciplinary teams, researchers often navigate multiple roles, shifting responsibilities depending on the context in which they operate [5]. Traditional persona models often fail to accommodate these fluid transitions, leading to gaps in infrastructure support and training programs.

The need to address these interdisciplinarity and fluidity challenges is notable in cross-domain consortia such as NFDI4Health, NFDI4DS, and Base4NFDI. These initiatives span multiple (sub)disciplines, requiring infrastructure solutions that are not only technically robust but also contextually adaptable. Training programs must be flexible enough to support researchers and other academic professionals as they move across roles and domains while ensuring that resources remain accessible and practical for a diverse user base.

To advance research on personas in interdisciplinary and changing contexts, we propose a structured, collaborative approach.

Firstly, we will consolidate existing knowledge by compiling research on personas within the NFDI consortia mentioned before. This includes analyzing prior studies and reviewing

available raw data that provide insights into researchers' experiences. For the knowledge distillation process, we will use, in particular, Base4NFDI training materials [6]. Secondly, we will review published studies on personas [7,8], focusing particularly on information relevant to interdisciplinary contexts. Another valuable source of information includes online research resources of different NFDI consortia [e.g. 4Biodiv, 4Ing, 4DS].

Using this shared knowledge as a foundation, we will develop a map of existing research on personas in interdisciplinary and changing settings and identify gaps relevant to our three consortia, as well as to the broader NFDI community.

In parallel to this research process, we will organize cross-consortia discussions on training specific to the challenges of interdisciplinary research. Initially, we will focus on collaboration between data scientists and medical researchers, identifying typical bottlenecks and communication difficulties. We will compile and promote existing training materials relevant across communities. AI Ethics, already addressed in NFDI4DS [2] and NFDI4Health [9], serves as a key example of a necessary training topic for cross-domain collaborative work, as computational models in medicine require ethical considerations for human data, as well as a responsible development of AI-based solutions.

By focusing on the challenges of interdisciplinary collaboration and the variability of researcher roles, this initiative aims to create a more effective research infrastructure. Through collective effort, we can develop tailored training programs, optimize infrastructure usability, and enhance support mechanisms that align with the realities of modern research environments. Strengthening our understanding of personas within the complex settings of the consortia will serve as the first step toward a global NFDI discussion on interdisciplinary research challenges and will contribute to building an inclusive and adaptable research ecosystem within the NFDI consortia. As a developing EOSC node, NFDI will be well-positioned to address interdisciplinary service development, a priority outlined in the Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) for 2026-27 [MAR].

Keywords: Interdisciplinary, Collaborative, Requirements Engineering, Persona, UX, NFDI, Research Infrastructure, Design Thinking

Resources

- [4Biodiv] <https://www.nfdi4biodiversity.org/de/personas/>
- [4Ing] https://nfdi4ing.de/home/25_aboutus/25_archetypes/
- [4DS] <https://www.nfdi4datascience.de/community/requirements-elicitation/personas/>
- [MAR] https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/MAR_2025-27_draft.pdf

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Conceptualization: EK; Investigation: all co-authors; Methodology: EK, JD, OB, SS; Writing – original draft: EK; Writing – review & editing: all co-authors

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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